

Molybdenum: Part I. Quinoline Carboxylic Acid Complexes of Molybdenum (V).*

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A short summary of the types of known molybdenum (V) Complexes is presented. A series of new Complexes of oxo-molybdenum (V) of varied types with quinoline 2-Carboxylic acid and quinoline 8-Carboxylic acids are reported. Besides analytical results, oxidation state of molybdenum in these Complexes, magnetic properties and absorption spectra are included and discussed. Tentative assignments of the structures have also been made.

The following types of Complexes have been isolated and characterised:

- (1) $\text{MoOCl}_2\text{Q}_2 \cdot \text{XHCl}$, (2) $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})\text{Q}_2$, (3) $\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \text{XH}_2\text{O}$, (4) $\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \text{X}$
(5) $\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \text{LL}$, MoO_2Q and (6) $\text{MoOCl}_2\text{Q} \cdot \text{LL}$, MoOCl_2Q .

(Where QH=Quinoline 2-Carboxylic acid or quinoline 8-Carboxylic etc; X=Pyridine; α -Picoline; quinoline; thiourea etc; LL=O-phenanthroline; κ, κ' -dipyridyl).

The Complexes are all quite stable to permit handling in air.

This series of studies has its origin in sustained investigations that are being carried out in our Laboratory on Oxo-vanadium(IV) Complexes of a wide variety with unusual Coordinating ligands¹⁻⁷. This and few other following communications will cover our interests in the Coordination Chemistry of oxo-molybdenum Complexes.

Since our undertaking of this project, we have been happily surprised to note the vast amount of interest that is being increasingly exhibited in the Coordination Chemistry of Oxo-molybdenum(V)⁸⁻¹⁷. One major reason for this revival of interest of Coordination

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15. Allen and Neumann, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 4, 1612.
16. Spitsyn, Kolli and Wen-hisa, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 9, 54.
17. Sievers and Bailar, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 174.

Chemistry in Oxo-molybdenum(V) is certainly the advent of ligand-field theory, which has been a powerful tool in interpreting absorption spectra. The need for newer syntheses, therefore arose, which alone could set varied fields around Oxo-molybdenum(V) resulting in different spectral characteristics. Before we go about presenting our own results, we briefly summarise the existing position with regard to Oxo-molybdenum(V).

We present the following classification of the hitherto known complexes:

1. $\text{MoOCl}_2 \text{L}_2$; where L = a Unidentate, neutral donor ligand, such as, triphenylphosphine oxide¹³, dimethyl sulphoxide¹³.
2. $\text{MoOCl}_2 \text{(LL)}_2$; where L = a neutral, bidentate ligand such as α, α' -dipyridyl¹⁴, O-phenanthroline¹⁵.
3. (LL) MoOCl_2 . O. MoOCl_2 (LL); where L = a neutral, bidentate donor e.g. α, α' -dipyridyl¹⁴.
4. (LL) $\text{MoOCl} \left\langle \begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{O} \end{array} \right\rangle \text{MoOCl}$ (LL); where LL = neutral, bidentate donor e.g. α, α' -dipyridyl¹⁴.
5. MoOCl (AB)_2 ; where AB = a bidentate, monobasic acid e.g. 8-hydroxyquinoline¹².
6. MoO (OH) (AB)_2 ; where AB is the same ligand as in (5).
7. $\text{Mo (OH)}_2 \text{(AB)}_2$; where AB = a bidentate, monobasic acid e.g. acetylaceton¹².
8. $\text{MoO (OH) Cl}_2 \text{LL}$; where LL = a neutral bidentate donor e.g. O-phenanthroline¹⁵.
9. $\text{M}[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]$; where M = K or $\frac{1}{2}$ Ba¹⁶
10. $\text{M}_2[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7(\text{EDTA})] \times \text{H}_2\text{O}$; where M = Na, EDTA = ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid¹⁷.
11. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7(\text{tu})_2 \text{x}_4]$; where tu = thiourea¹⁶ and $\text{x} = \text{Cl}^-/\text{Br}^-$

Besides the interest involved in the syntheses of such Mo(V) Complexes and interpreting the absorption spectra of the Complexes, one other interest attaches itself to the study of these Complexes. In molybdenum(V) complexes, there is often noticed a considerable extent of polymerisation, which is reflected in a subnormal magnetic moment. In those complexes, where a monomer structure prevails, the Complexes respond to a full unpaired electron ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.73 \text{ B.M.}$) as demanded by a spin formula only. Instead many other Complexes exist, which have registered much lower moment values. These have been regarded as important instances, where considerable spin pairing occurs due to bridging of two or more octahedra by oxygen or chlorine. Thus magnetic moment may be regarded as diagnostic of monomeric or polymeric nature of such complexes.

It was in the light of the above results that we have undertaken a broad programme of studies on molybdenum(V) Complexes. We considered that the existing literature was distinctly poor in that very few inner metallic ligands have been experimented upon. We thought that a greater variation in the pattern of the complexes could be achieved with inner metallic ligands rather than with entirely neutral donors. Moreover we found that there was practically no report on mixed ligand complexes of Oxo-molybdenum(V). Our interest on mixed ligand complexes of Cobalt(III) as also of Vanadium(IV) has added further enthusiasm to the present study of Oxo-molybdenum(V) Complexes.

We have completed our studies with a large number of quinoline and pyridine carboxylic acids as also with oxine and substituted oxines as the inner metallic complexing ligands. Besides, studies on Oxo-molybdenum(V) Complexes with two substituted o-phenanthrolines as also some ligand exchange reactions have been made. The complexes being reported in this first paper of the series are grouped as follows:

- I. $\text{MoOClQ}_2 \cdot \text{xHCl}$ (where QH = Quinoline 2-(or 8) Carboxylic acid
- II. MoO(OH)Q_2 (where QH = Quinoline 2-Carboxylic acid
- III. $\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \text{xH}_2\text{O}$ (where QH = Quinoline 2-(or 8) Carboxylic acid

- IV. $\text{MoO}_2\text{Q}_2\text{X}$ (where QH=Quinoline 2-Carboxylic acid. X=Pyridine; β - or α -picoline; quinoline, quinaldine, acetonitrile, & thiourea).
 V. $\text{MoO}_2\text{Q}_2\text{LL}$. MoO_2Q (where QH=Quinoline 2-Carboxylic acid and LL=O-Phenanthroline).
 VI. MoOCl_2Q (LL) MoOCl_2Q (where QH=Quinoline 2- (or 8) Carboxylic acid and LL=O-Phenanthroline; α α' -dipyridyl).

We would now proceed to describe the preparation and properties of the above new Complexes.

I. $\text{MoOCl}_2\text{Q}_2 \cdot \text{XHCl}$: In our all studies as in others too, we observed that reactions of Molybdenum(V) are extremely susceptible to solvolysis. We have used the well known green coloured crystalline compound, $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ as the starting source of Oxo-molybdenum(V). The green compound and quinaldinic acid were treated in anhydrous alcohol and in CO_2 atmosphere in the cold, when an intense marooned crystalline material, $\text{MoOCl}_2\text{Q}_2 \cdot 0.5 \text{HCl}$ was finally produced. The dried material is sparingly soluble in ethanol and other organic solvents. The subnormal magnetic susceptibility points to some degree of polymerisation and the complex may be represented as

The seven coordinated structure is preferred because of the tenacity with which the HCl is retained (no loss at 120°C nor any decomposition) and the strong acid reaction and high conductance ($180 \text{ ohms}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$) when dissolved in methanol. The latter reaction may, however, be responded by the first structure through alcholsolysis:—

The Complex provides an oxidation number of of. +5 for molybdenum and reveals a strong molybdenyl band at 970cm^{-1} . The corresponding quinoline 8-carboxylate, crystallises with 2HCl and the compound decomposes on heating to around 130° . The sparing solubility in methanol has made difficult measurements of its conductance.

II. $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})\text{Q}_2$: The above described complex $\text{MoOCl}_2\text{Q}_2 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{HCl}$ (where QH=quinaldinic acid) when treated with aqueous ethanol (rectified spirit) solution of quinaldinic acid, there is liberation of HCl due to hydrolysis. The presence of quinaldinic acid appears essential to have a pure product of the formula $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})\text{Q}_2$, otherwise products of somewhat indefinite composition are obtained. Once again the Complex registers a diamagnetic value and shows the usual molybdenyl band at 970cm^{-1} besides showing a broad band around 3500cm^{-1} which is partly due to OH absorption and partly due to the presence of ligand vibrations around this band. The suggested structure thus is:

CHART I

General Scheme of reactions of Mo (V) with quinaldnic acid.

(QH=Quinaldnic acid; Py=Pyridine and O-Phen=O-Phenanthroline)

TABLE I.

Magnetic measurements and oxidation numbers

Temp. = 30°C.

No.	Compounds	Colour	Oxidation number	Dia. Corr $\times 10^6$	χ_m Corr $\times 10^6$	μ_{eff} (B.M.)*
1.	$\text{MoOCl}_4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{HCl}$	Maroon	+5	221.6	221.6	0.73
2.	$[\text{Mo}_2\text{OCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{HCl}]$	Light orange	+5.2	256.1	109.7	0.32
3.	$[\text{MoO}(\text{OH})\text{Q}_2]$	Deep orange	+5.2	—	—	Diamagnetic
4.	$[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q}], \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light orange	+4.9	—	—	"
5.	$[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q}^1]$	"	+5.1	—	—	"
6.	$[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \text{Py}]$	Orange red	+5	—	—	"
7.	$[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \alpha\text{-Picoline}]$	Light orange	+5	—	—	"
8.	$[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \beta\text{-Picoline}]$	Red	+5	—	—	"
9.	$[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \text{Quinoline}]$	Orange	+5	—	—	"
10.	$[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \text{Quinaldine}]$	Light orange	+5	186.0	264.0	0.80
11.	$[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \text{CH CN}]$	Orange	+5.2	—	—	Diamagnetic
12.	$[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \text{tu}]$	"	+5.3	—	—	"
13.	$[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \frac{1}{2} (\text{O-Phen})]$	"	+5.2	—	—	"
14.	$[\text{MoOCl}_4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} (\text{O-Phen})]$	Maroon	+5	187.8	57.1	0.21
15.	$[\text{MoOCl}_4(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N}) \cdot \frac{1}{2} (\text{dipy})]$	"	+5.0	—	—	Diamag.
16.	$[\text{MoOCl}_4 \cdot (\text{Ph}_3\text{P})]$	Black	+5.1	351.3	56.4	0.37
17.	$\text{MoOCl}_4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} (\text{O-Phen})$	Maroon	+5.2	186.7	162.0	0.63

*Calculated from χ_m corr. using Curie equation, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84 (\chi_m \text{corr.} \times T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ (QH=Quinaldnic acid; Q¹=Quinoline 8-Carboxylic acid; ph₃P=Triphenyl Phosphine and tu=thiourea).

V. $\text{MoOCl}_4 \cdot \text{Q} \cdot \text{LLW} \text{MoOCl}_4 \cdot \text{Q}$: This series of compounds with LL standing for O-Phenanthroline has been obtained for both the quinaldnic acid and the quinoline 8-Carboxylic acid ligands. Thus when the molybdenum(V) chloride and the reagents are refluxed with anhydrous ethanol and the clear solution heated with half mole of O-Phenanthroline,

there occurs immediately a separation of dark maroon red crystalline product, identified as above. The reactions presumably are:

The oxidation number of molybdenum in both the cases is around +5 but the magnetic moment is subnormal. This property coupled with insolubility in all common organic solvents once again predicts substantial polymerisation in the system, being brought about by the presence of a strong bidentate O-Phenanthroline. The above bridged complexes are unique and hitherto have no parallel in the molybdenum(V) chemistry.

VI. MoO_2Q . LL. MoO_2Q : The above described phenanthroline bridged complexes sever their halogen bonds when treated with anhydrous sodium acetate and result in the formation of dull coloured bridged compounds of this above type. Again the oxidation numbers are +5, magnetic moments below normal and the complex insoluble in organic solvents thus suggesting the following configuration:

The above configuration does not seem to be unreasonable because, when two Mo(V) octahedra share an edge, O-Phenanthroline effectively occupies only CIS positions.

FIG. 1

We would wish now to describe briefly the visible spectra of some representative members of the many Complexes that we have described in the foregoing paragraphs. As the complexes are mostly insoluble in all common organic solvents, we had obtained several reflectance spectra. The spectra of Molybdenum(V) Complexes have been discussed

by several workers following the studies initiated on the $[\text{MoOCl}_5]^{2-18}$. The complexes mostly exhibit three distinct absorption bands in the ligand field region. The low intensity absorption peaks in the long wave length region are certainly due to the first crystal field transitions $2B_g \rightarrow 2E(I)$ ($dxy, \rightarrow dxz, dyz$). This transition in our selected complexes are spread over the region $730\text{m}\mu \leftrightarrow 760\text{m}\mu$ ($13,698\text{cm}^{-1}$ to $13,157\text{cm}^{-1}$). The second crystal field transition found to lie around wave length $500\text{-}540\text{m}\mu$ ($20,000\text{cm}^{-1}$ to $18,518\text{cm}^{-1}$) and are due to the transition $2g_g \rightarrow 2g_g$ ($dxy \rightarrow dx^2-y^2$). In intensity these second peaks are next to the longest wave length peaks. The third peaks have been observed around $420\text{-}450\text{m}\mu$ ($23,571\text{cm}^{-1}$ to $22,000\text{cm}^{-1}$) and are almost of equal intensity to the second bands. Since the reflectance spectra do not allow accurate estimation of the extinction values, we are not quite certain as to the extent of contribution these third bands have from the charge transfer bands. Because of their comparable intensity these may, not quite unreasonably, be identified with the expected third ligand field band $2g_g \rightarrow 2A_1$ ($dxy \rightarrow dx^2$). In two of the compounds for which we are reporting the spectra the second band is not quite resolved and

TABLE II
Reflectance Spectra of the Complexes

Complex	λ_{max} (m μ)	Wave number ν (cm $^{-1}$)	Probable assignment
1. (1. $[\text{MoOCl}_4 \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{HCl}]$)	750	13,300	${}^2B_g \rightarrow {}^2E(I)$ ($dxy \rightarrow dxz, dyz$)
	525	19,040	${}^2B_g \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ ($dxy \rightarrow dx^2-y^2$)
	450	22,000	${}^2B_g \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ ($dxy \rightarrow dx^2$)
2. $[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q Py}]$	750	13,300	${}^2B_g \rightarrow {}^2E(I)$ ($dxy \rightarrow dxz, dyz$)
	400	25,000	${}^2B_g \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ ($dxy \rightarrow dx^2$)
3. $[\text{MoOCl}_2\text{Q} \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{O-Phen})]$	725	13,790	${}^2B_g \rightarrow {}^2E(I)$ ($dxy \rightarrow dxz, dyz$)
	(475-525)	(21,526-19,047)	${}^2B_g \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ ($dxy \rightarrow dx^2-y^2$)
	400	25,000	${}^2B_g \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ ($dxy \rightarrow dx^2$)
4. $[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q}]$	750	13,300	${}^2B_g \rightarrow {}^2E(I)$ ($dxy \rightarrow dxz, dyz$)

(where Q = Quinoline 8-Carboxylic acid)

appears to have been buried under the tail of the third band. The spectral characteristics appear to be in line with other bridged Oxo-molybdenum(V) complexes¹⁸. We have interpreted the spectra on a monomer orbital scheme. In view of our complexes exhibiting magnetic moments, often below 0.4 B.M. a strong spin-spin interaction is suggested. In such cases dimer molecular orbital model is required and singlet ground state exists. The lowest transitions would still be between d-type orbitals but spread over two Oxo-molybdenum (V) units^{18c}.

In order to throw more light into the mechanism of the spin-pairing, elaborate magnetic investigations at varied temperatures will be necessary. Unfortunately with our present experimental set-up, we are unable to achieve this.

EXPERIMENTAL

Quinaldinic acid was prepared from quinaldine (B.D.H.) by following Hammick's procedure¹⁹ and was recrystallised from hot glacial acetic acid, furnishing light cream

18. Gray and Hare, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 963; 1962, 1, 831.

18a. Mitchell, *Quart. Revs.*, 1966, 20, 103.

19. Hammick, *J. Chem., Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2882.

coloured fine needles. Quinoline 8-Carboxylic acid was prepared by condensing anthranilic acid and O-nitrobenzoic acid in presence of anhydrous glycerol and conc. H_2SO_4 and finally purified from chloroform²⁰. Ammonium oxopentachloro-molybdate(V) (emerald green) was synthesised by following standard procedure²¹ and purity checked by analysis. All refluxing was done on a sand bath and no special precaution was taken to exclude air and moisture.

1. *Oxo-Chloro-bis quinaldinato-molybdenum (V), semihydrochloride (maroon)*.—Quinaldinic acid (0.53 g.), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (15 ml.) was filtered and deaerated by carbon dioxide gas for 15 minutes while being cooled in ice water. Ammonium oxo-pentachloro-molybdate (0.98 g), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (15 ml), was filtered through sintered funnel and was added to the ice cold quinaldinic acid solution. Immediately, a deep maroon coloured precipitate settled while CO_2 passed through along with cooling of the reaction vessel. After 15-20 minutes the reaction product was transferred on to a sintered funnel and filtered in CO_2 atmosphere, washed with little anhydrous ethanol and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator. Found: Mo 19.02%; N, 5.8%; Cl, 10.6%. $MoOCl(C_{10}H_6O_2N)_2O$. † HCl requires Mo, 18.7%; 5.5%; Cl, 10.4%.

2. *Oxo-Chloro-bis-quinoline 8-Carboxylate molybdenum(V) dihydrochloride (light orange)*.—Quinoline 8-Carboxylic acid (1.7 g), dissolved in cold chloroform-anhydrous ethanol (10 ml+15 ml) mixture, was filtered and was deaerated by CO_2 in the cold. Ammonium Oxo-Penta chloromolybdate (V) (0.65 g), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (15 ml), was filtered through sintered funnel and this solution was added to ice cold reagent solution. Immediately an orange precipitate settled while CO_2 passed through. After 15-20 minutes, the reaction product was filtered through a sintered funnel in CO_2 atmosphere, washed with little alcohol-chloroform mixture, finally dried in a vacuum desiccator. Found: Mo, 17.14%, N, 5.2%; Cl, 19.02%. $MoOCl(C_{10}H_6O_2N)_2, 2HCl$ requires Mo, 17.02%; N, 4.9%; Cl, 18.86%.

3. *Oxo-Hydroxo-bisquinaldinato-molybdenum(V) (orange)*. Oxo-chloro-bisquinaldinato-molybdenum(V), semihydrochloride (maroon) was prepared as described before. It was sucked dry and refluxed with rectified spirit (10 ml) solution of quinaldinic acid (0.35 gm) for 15 minutes when maroon compound changed to orange. It was then filtered and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Found: Mo, 19.92%; N, 5.88%. $MoO(OH)(C_{10}H_6O_2N)_2$ requires Mo, 20.4%; N, 5.90%.

4. *Dioxo-Monoquinaldinato-molybdenum(V), Monohydrate (light orange)*.—Ammonium oxo-pentachloro molybdate (0.65 g), dissolved in rectified spirit (15 ml), was filtered and added to a rectified spirit (10 ml) solution of quinaldinic acid (.4 g). Immediately, an orange precipitate resulted. This was refluxed for 10 minutes to a deep red solution. The pH of this solution was below 4.0. Some anhydrous sodium acetate (2.0 g) was added and the solution further refluxed, when pH rose to around 7.0. The crystalline precipitate was filtered, triturated with distilled water, filtered again and dried over $CaCl_2$. Found: Mo, 30.66%; N, 4.20%; H_2O (by loss at $110^\circ C$) 5.2%. $MoO_2(C_{10}H_6O_2N)H_2O$ requires Mo, 30.0%; N, 4.36%; H_2O , 5.6%.

5. *Dioxo-Mono quinoline 8-carboxylate-molybdenum(V) (light orange)*.—Quinoline 8-Carboxylic acid (.4 g) and pyridine (2.5 ml) was refluxed for 5 minutes and was then

20. Campbell, Kerwin, Laforge and Campbell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1845.

21. Palmer, "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", Oxford University 1934, pp. 406-408.

filtered through sintered funnel. Ammonium oxo-pentachloromolybdate (.65 g), dissolved in rectified spirit (15 ml), was filtered from NH_4Cl and the solution added to the pyridine solution of the ligand. Immediately, a light orange precipitate settled. This was refluxed for 10 minutes, filtered, washed several times with rectified spirit to remove excess pyridine and finally dried over CaCl_2 . Found: Mo, 32.30%; N, 4.80%. $\text{MoO}_5(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})$ requires Mo, 32.3%; N, 4.67%.

6. *Pyridine-dioxo-monoquinaldinate-molybdenum(V) (orange-red)*—Ammonium oxo-pentachloromolybdate (.65 g), dissolved in rectified spirit (15 ml) was filtered and this solution was added to a quinaldine acid (.4 g) solution in rectified spirit (10 ml). Immediately, an orange precipitate formed. This was then refluxed to a clear red solution, pyridine (3.0 ml) was added and further refluxed for 10 minutes. On cooling shining, orange-red crystals formed. These were filtered, washed several times with rectified spirit to remove adhered pyridine and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: Mo, 25.20%; N, 7.60%. $\text{MoO}_5(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})$ requires Mo, 25.20%; N, 7.30%.

The substance liberates pyridine on heating with sodium hydroxide.

7. α -*Picoline-dioxo-monoquinaldinate-molybdenum(V) (light orange)* was obtained as above using α -picoline in place of pyridine. Found: Mo, 24.4%; N, 7.5%. $\text{MoO}_5(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N})(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})$ requires Mo, 24.8%; N, 7.1%.

8. β -*Picoline-dioxo-monoquinaldinate-molybdenum(V) (red)*—was obtained as above using β -picoline in place of α -picoline. Found: Mo, 24.90%; N, 7.20%. $\text{MoO}_5(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N})(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})$ requires: Mo, 24.80%; N, 7.10%.

9. *Quinoline-dioxo-monoquinaldinate-molybdenum(V) (orange)*—was obtained as above using quinoline in place of α -picoline. Found: Mo, 21.9%; N, 6.45%. $\text{MoO}_5(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N})$ requires Mo, 22.2%; N, 6.40%.

10. *Quinaldine-dioxo-monoquinaldinate-molybdenum(V), monohydrate (light orange)*—was obtained as above using quinaldine in place of quinoline. Found: Mo, 20.44%; N, 5.80%, H_2O (by loss at 105°) 4.1%. $\text{MoO}_5(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mo, 20.62%; N, 6.24% H_2O , 3.86%.

11. *Acetonitrile-dioxo-monoquinaldinate-molybdenum(V) (orange)*—was obtained as above using acetonitrile in place of quinaldine. Found: Mo, 28.1%; N, 7.93%. $\text{MoO}_5(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})$ requires Mo, 29.9%; N, 8.14%.

12. *Thiourea-dioxo-monoquinaldinate-molybdenum(V) (orange)*—was obtained as above using thiourea (.65 g) in place of acetonitrile. Found: Mo, 25.05%; N, 10.85%. S, 8.9%. $\text{MoO}_5(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})(\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{S})$ requires Mo, 25.53%; N, 11.1%; S, 8.8%. The complex was found to be free from any chloride.

13. μ -*O-Phenanthroline-tetraoxo-di-quinaldinate-dimolybdenum(V) (orange)*—Quinaldine acid (.4 g) in rectified spirit (10 ml) was mixed with filtered solution of ammonium oxo-pentachloro-molybdate (.65 g) in rectified spirit (15 ml). Immediately a precipitate formed. This was then refluxed to a clear solution. O-Phenanthroline (.18 g), dissolved in rectified spirit (10 ml), was added to the above solution when a maroon precipitate settled. To it anhydrous sodium acetate (2-3 gms) was added and refluxed when an orange precipitate formed. This was filtered, triturated with distilled water and again filtered and dried

over CaCl_2 . Found: Mo, 24.61%; N, 7.08%. $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ (O-Phen) requires Mo, 24.55%; N, 7.10%.

14. μ -O-Phenanthroline-dioxo tetrachlorodiquinaldinato-di-molybdenum (V) (maroon)—Quinaldinic acid (.4 g) dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (15 ml) was mixed with a filtered solution of ammonium⁴- δ -pentachloro molybdate (.65 g) dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (15 ml). This was then refluxed for 15 minutes and O-Phenanthroline (.8 g), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (15 ml) was added to this solution. Immediately a heavy crystalline maroon compound settled. This was refluxed for 10 minutes, cooled, filtered, washed several times with anhydrous ethanol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: Mo, 22.2%; N, 5.9%. Cl, 15.83%. $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ (O-Phen) requires Mo, 21.5%, N, 6.2%, Cl, 15.8%.

15. μ - κ , κ' -dipyridyl-dioxo-tetrachloro-dequinaldinato-dimolybdenum (V) (maroon)—was obtained as described in the preparation of μ -O-Phenanthroline-dioxo-tetrachlorodiquinaldinato-dimolybdenum(V) by using κ , κ' -dipyridyl (.14 g) in place of o-phenanthroline. Found: Mo, 22.8%; N, 6.2%; Cl, 17.0%. $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ (dipy) requires Mo, 22.2%; N, 6.4%, Cl, 16.4%. Using even a slight excess dipyridyl (over 0.14g) lowers the purity of the ultimate product.

16. Triphenyl phosphine oxo-dichloro monoquinaldinato molybdenum (V) (black)—was obtained as above using excess triphenylphosphine in place of O-Phenanthroline. Found: Mo, 17.0%; N, 2.5%; Cl, 12.0%. $\text{MoOCl}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{P})$ requires Mo, 16.4%; N, 2.26%, Cl, 11.45%.

17. μ -O-Phenanthroline-dioxo tetrachloro-diquinoline 8-carboxylate di-molybdenum (V) (maroon)—was obtained as described in the preparation of μ -O-Phenanthroline-dioxo-tetrachloro-diquinaldinato dimolybdenum(V) by using quinoline 8-carboxylic acid (.5 g) in place of quinaldinic acid. Found: Mo, 21.00%; N, 6.0%; Cl, 15.7%. $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ (O-Phen) requires Mo, 21.39%; N, 6.2%; Cl, 15.8%.

Analytical methods:—Molybdenum content was determined either (a) by decomposing the complex with equal volumes of conc. H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 and then after adjusting the pH precipitating molybdenum with oxine, and finally weighing as $[\text{MoO}_4(\text{oxine})_2]$ or (b) by decomposing the complex with alkali-hydrogen peroxide and then precipitating and weighing as $[\text{MoO}_4(\text{oxine})_2]$

Estimation of chloride was made by way of double precipitation. Molybdenum was removed as oxinate and then chloride precipitated as AgCl . This was filtered, dissolved in ammonia and reprecipitated with dil. HNO_3 and finally weighed as AgCl .

Nitrogen was estimated by combustion technique.

Magnetic measurements—The magnetic susceptibility was determined by the Gouy method using a semi-micro Mettler Balance for measuring the difference in weight with a field strength of 8.57×10^3 gauss. Diamagnetic corrections were taken from Selwood²².

The IR spectra were scanned on a Beckman spectrophotometer model IR -4 using NaCl prism.

22. Selwood, "Magnetochemistry", P91 (1958).

Oxidation state of molybdenum in the Complexes was determined by dissolving a known weight of the sample in excess of acidified ferric alum solution under magnetic stirring in a stoppered iodine flask. After complete dissolution (which sometimes needed more than an hour), the ferrous content was determined by usual permanganate titration. A blank was also run with quinoline carboxylic acids, which however consumed very little permanganate.

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